

EDUCATION TRANSFER KNOWLEDGE 11.

Training Contents for Student teachers,
Academic and School Mentors

Project Information

Project acronym: EKT

Project title: Education Knowledge Transfer

Agreement number: 612414-EPP-1-2019-1-ES-EPPKA2-KA

Authoring partner: University College of Teacher Education Vienna

Date of preparation:

May 2021 (pre-pilot version)

March 2023 (post-pilot version)

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Please cite as: Revyakina, E. (2022). Training Contents for Student teachers, Academic and School Mentors Output 11. Vienna: University College of Teacher Education Vienna.

This is Output 11 of O27 in the EKT Output Series. All public outputs in the series are available from the project website: <https://ektproject.eu>

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1. INTRODUCTION

As part of the EKT project, University College of Teacher Education Vienna has taken on the role of leading in the development of a small private online course (SPOC) on introducing the key school placement (SP) actors - student teachers (prospective teachers), academic mentors (lectures) and school mentors (school teachers, cooperating teachers, mentors) – to the EKT system, and engaging with the methodology that would support SP in the three key areas:

- 1. The cooperation and collaboration between academic mentors and school teachers.**
- 2. The individualized follow-up of students in school practicum.**
- 3. The reflective practice of student teachers.**

Thus, we aim to create a SPOC framework covering ideas and activities that will be useful to student teachers, academic mentors and school mentors during the SP as well engaging the key actors with the EKT system. These cover activities around the key phases of SP as described in WP3 for academic mentors, school mentors and student teachers. The focus throughout is on capacity building for meaningful professional dialogue and reflective practice.

The underpinning purpose of the work is not simply the making of the SPOC to support the EKT system, but it is to develop a flexible methodology to enhance professional dialogue, student teachers' agency and promote an action-oriented reflection among student teachers. The literature and data gathered during WP2 offered a basis on which to identify sets of the key ideas and concepts that we use to define and develop the framework for the EKT SPOC content and tasks.

In summary: the purpose of this Report is to show work in relation to O11 Contents for Academic mentors, School mentors and Student Teachers.

2. DESIGN PROCESS

The University College of Teacher Education Vienna EKT team presented the SPOC design approach to the partners during the December workshop 2020 drawing from WP2 O5 and literature review around SP.

The presented approach was based on the following **principles and ideas**:

- Well-integrated pedagogical approaches.
- Content and activities that allow for flexibility and provide opportunity for reflection and professional dialogue.
- An approach that fosters communication and collaboration opportunities within EKT partner universities and SP schools.

Further feedback and ideas were gathered from the EKT partners during the first months of 2021. These had to be aligned with the evolving functionalities of the EKT Platform. The feedback from the academic partners on the first proposal and the conversations with the technical board informed the Outline of the SPOC contents and activities.

After the first cycle of pilot, the contents of the SPOC were added with an additional information on the changes of the EKT Platform (improvements made after the first pilot), and Unit 4, inspired by the need to respond to further development of the methodological framework (O3) and the new tool on the EKT Platform, Content Creation Tool, Chamilo Studio. Feedback from the academic partners and student teachers (based on the EKT Survey and focus group interviews) informed the Final Version of the EKT SPOC.

3. THE EKT SPOC ARCHITECTURE: THE UNDERPINNING DESIGN

As noted briefly above, the underpinning purpose of the work on the EKT SPOC is not simply the making of the SPOC to support the EKT system, but to develop a flexible methodology to enhance professional dialogue, student teachers' agency and support an action-oriented reflection among student teachers; importantly to create a meaningful learning experience for all the SPOC participants.

The complexity of the task is:

- 1. Diverse SP contexts in each EKT partner institution.**
- 2. The aim to engage three target groups in the SPOC:** student teachers, academic mentors and school mentors, and considering how these different roles are represented in the EKT system and with which affordances they are provided;
- 3.** The aim to **reflect both primary and secondary SP ITE programme** needs and all ISP cycles needs. Much of the work has been to identify and examine sources in the literature and in the practice-world of SP teacher education that could contribute to building the SPOC framework that would respond to that complexity. Furthermore, the SPOC design relies hugely on project study (WP2), methodological framework (WP3), and the evolution of the EKT platform (WP4) which meant taking on board all the developments in those WPs as they evolve. Finally, considering that SPOC is part of the pilot one of its goals – as we see it – to facilitate the evaluation of the experience of the EKT system of the key target groups.

Thus, the decisions around content and activities that come to constitute the **initial EKT SPOC framework** are informed by the underpinning purpose and the complexity described above, the EKT system, the methodological framework presented in WP3 and plans for the Pilots. Discussions in the University College of Teacher Education Vienna EKT Team and staff have been around finding the most flexible and manageable approach (specifically in terms of workload for the academic mentors and school mentors) that is activity-driven and collaborative and that would ensure the set goals are achieved. The chosen strategy was formulated as

- 1.** To support communication channels, and interaction between and within the three target groups through 'collaborative activities';
- 2.** To provide opportunities to try out the tools in the platform ('learning by doing' approach).

We draw on a **number of sources** that direct the emerging SPOC framework. The first, and most defining source, for our work on the SPOC architecture has been the Methodological Framework (WP3); in particular, the description of the activities that academic mentors, school mentors and teacher students undertake at different stages of the SP. Stage 2 described in WP3 as “Preparation before the stay in the schools” was identified as key since the SPOC needs to train the three target groups in the EKT System as well as enhance the communication channels between the three target groups from the very beginning.

Further, in the University College of Teacher Education Vienna Team it was discussed how and if the SPOC could play a role in engaging the ‘learners’ in meaningful professional dialogues and collaborative reflections - supported by technology, and importantly in adding a value to the SP experience. It was decided to include into the contents and activities **elements of Action Research (AR) for teachers** with a focus on **collaborative reflections** and **analytical stance** on one’s own practice with the goal to understand one’s own practice and improve certain aspects in focus (Elliot 1991). The choice to try out elements of Action Research as a questioning approach draws on the core premises that:

1. Developing the ability to reflect about practice requires that preservice teachers learn to question existing practice, and consider alternatives (Ross 1987).
2. AR is a process that may be used to focus teaching questions, observations and reflections, and organize and interpret the multiple classroom data sources that reflect student learning (Moore 2007).
3. AR can be a method of daily inquiry and problem-solving in classrooms; and a method of bridging the theory and practice divide (Kitchen & Stevens 2008).

For the SPOC, we seek to use the elements of AR that would engage the student teachers in focusing their observations and reflections on an aspect of their teaching experience that is of interest to them in order for them to take responsibility and become more proactive through observations, reflection and inquiry into their practice; that would ask the student teachers to turn to theory and practice; and that would engage the student teachers in professional dialogue with the school teacher and academic mentor. **In summary, the design and development process leading to the current SPOC architecture has been outlined and discussed above. The final version of the Contents and Activities for the EKT SPOC is presented next.**

4. OUTLINE OF THE EKT SPOC

- **Duration:** apx. 3 weeks (one/two weeks prior to the SP, one/two weeks during the SP);
- **Time:** For student teachers each week around 3 hours; for the academic mentors and school mentors – from 1 hour to 3 hours.
- **Language:** English, German, Spanish, Portuguese
- **Year Group and in-school placement Cycle:** any

4.1. General Description

The SPOC has four Units. The key outputs of the SPOC Course are:

1. Collaborative Discussion of the SP Expectations and Plans

2. Students' self-introduction and reflection on values: why I decided to become a teacher

3. Students' mindmap around the focus for observation: as an expression of one's interest and reflection on theory and one's own teaching experience; as a starting point for pre-observation meeting;

4. Formulated **Research Question and Action-Oriented Reflection** developed by the student teachers with the support from academic mentors and school mentors around the following points (posted in Portfolio):

4.1. My Research Question/ Concern: framing the question and reasons to choose this one;

4.2. What I Know About This Issue:

A. Three valuable points I learned from the Literature Review.

B. Three valuable things I learned from Conversations with the Academic mentor, School mentor and peers.

C. A possible solution to my chosen issue / question / problem / concern.

5. Answer the question: **What am I going to try out during my in-school placement?**

The role of an academic mentor: to take part in discussions, to work with the school mentor to support the students with theoretical knowledge, monitor the students' reflective posts and give constructive feedback using the EKT platform tools. Academic mentors can choose to use Output 4 and 5 for assessment of in-school placement.

The role of a school mentor: to take part in discussions, to work with the academic mentor to support the students with practical advice, and give constructive feedback using the EKT platform tools.

Assessment in this online course is participatory mainly. This means that participation in discussions; feedback and responses to each other (students are asked to leave a meaningful comment on at least two other posts every time) construct 50% of success in the course.

In addition, the key product to complete the course successfully is Portfolio with entries made during the course based on the Tasks (50%), that needs to be exported and uploaded in the Documents Tool.

Picture 1. SPOC Learning Path

4.2. Unit 1. Introduction to the EKT Platform.

- **Objectives:** Start using the platform and working together on tasks
- **Method:** a collaborative task for student teachers, academic mentors and school mentors; mini-tasks to get started; a webinar.
- **Workload:** apx. 4 hours

Picture 2. Unit 1. Map of Tasks for Student Teachers and Mentors

4. Outline of the EKT SPOC

nr/name	Aim	Activity	involved	EKT Tools	workload
Task 1. Platform° overview VIDEO and QUIZ	Getting to know the EKT Platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Watch the short video about the platform and find out how it can support in-school placement. After watching the video, complete the quiz. 	ALL	Video embedded in the courseQuiz	15 min
Task 2 Netiquette Quiz	Thinking about common guidelines of online behaviour.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complete the Quiz 	ALL	Quiz	15 min
Task 3 Working with the Platform	Managing the platform (profile, password, calendar)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Watch two videos how to change Password, and edit Platform Profile. Change your password if you have not done it yet, and edit your profil. Watch the video around the Calendar Tool. Open the Calendar Tool and add to your calendar important events related to your school placement. Academic and school mentors are invited to share important events, lesson schedules and meetings with student teachers in the Calendar 	ALL	EKT Calendar Tool EKT Management Tool	30 min
Task 4 Expectations on In-School Placement	Working with the Document Tool and discussing expectations on in-school placement	<p>Task for Student Teachers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Watch the videos on the Document Tool and the Shared Folders in the Document Tool. Watch the video on how to Create and Share Folders and Documents. Go to the Document Tool and click on "Shares". Read the documents provided by your academic and school mentors in the folder "Documents for In-School Placement". Watch the video on how to use the Chat Tool in a document and work collaboratively on a document in the Documents Tool. Leave your comments and questions directly in the documents by using the Chat Tool. Look at the Expectations Checklist and try to fill it in. <p>Task for mentors:</p> <p>Go to the Document Tool. Please, create a folder called "Documents for In-School Placement" and share it with your students and with the school mentors; upload the documents you would like the students to read and discuss prior to the in-school placement.</p>	Separate tasks for student tachers and mentors	EKT Documents Tool	60 min
Task 5 Funny Anecdote	Sharing learning and teaching experiences via the Communication Tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Watch a short video on how to use the Communication Tool. Go to "funny anecdote" in the Communication Tool and write down an anecdote which describes a funny episode in your learning/teaching career. Read the anecdotes of some other participants. Leave at least three comments by using the @sign. 	Sharing learning and teaching experiences via the Communication Tool	EKT Communication Tool	30 min

Task 6 Video Call	Discussing expectations around the "In-School Placement" via the Video Call tool.	<p>Task for academic mentors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up a group welcome video call for your student(s) and the school mentor(s). Watch the videos on how to set up video calls from the Calendar Tool and how to start a call from the Communication Tool. • Discuss your and the others' expectations around the "in-school placement" during your group video call. Here you can find a suggested In-School Placement Checklist to discuss with the your students and school mentors. <p>Tasks for student teachers and school mentors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Watch a short video on the Video Call tool. • The academic mentors will organize a group welcome video call via the Calendar Tool. Take part in the Video Call. You can join from the Communication Tool. • Discuss your and the others' expectations around the "in-school placement" during your group video call. 	Sharing learning and teaching experiences via the Communication Tool	EKT Communication Tool (Video Conference) and Calendar tool	60 min
Task 7 Expectations Checklist	Reflecting on the conversation about "In-School Placement" expectations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on your conversations during the group video call, apply the necessary changes to the Expectations Checklist you started in Task 4. • Save and upload your document titled "(Your Name)'s Expectations Register" in the Shared Folder that was created in Task 4. • Academic and School Mentors, read your students' Expectations Register uploaded in the Shared Folder that was created in Task 4. 	Student teachers	EKT Document Tool	30mins
TOTAL WORKLOAD					4 HOURS

Checklist for Unit 1 Activities:

- I can use the Management Tool to edit my profile and password.
- I can create, share and work on files in the Document Tool.
- I can organise my work with the Calendar Tool.
- I can use the Communication Tool to have group or private chats.
- I can take part in and organise Video Calls.
- I am aware of the in-school placement expectations of my mentors.

4.3. Unit 2. Action Research in the Classroom

- **Objectives:** learn about Action Research and how this method of ‘self-development’ can help to reflect on teaching practice; work with ePortfolio and do some reflective writing on teaching/learning experiences as well as on values in education.
- **Method:** A number of challenge questions to stimulate dialogue and reflection.
- **Workload for students:** 3 hours; **for academic mentors and school mentors:** 1 hour.

Picture 3. Tasks for Unit 2.

4. Outline of the EKT SPOC

nr/name	Aim	Activities	Involved	EKT tool	workload
Task 1 Text, Video & Quiz on Action Research	Getting to know Action Research and Action Research Cycle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Read the background information on Action Research (AR). Watch the video "Introduction to Action Research". Then complete the quiz. 	Student teachers	Video quiz	15 min
Task 2 Video & Quiz on the AR Cycle	Getting to know the Action Research cycle and the adapted AR cycle for teachers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Watch the video on the AR cycle. Complete the quiz by matching the steps of the AR cycle. 	Student teachers	Video quiz	15 min
Task 3 ePortfolio Entry	Working with the ePortfolio Tool	<p>Tasks for student teachers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Watch the tutorial videos on the ePortfolio Tool: Overview; Key Actions in the ePortfolio; Commenting Functionalities. Make your first ePortfolio entry answering the questions "Why did you decide to become a teacher?" "Did you have a previous in-school placement training? If yes, what did you learn from your previous training" under the tag "values" and choose Section "Reflections" Phase Preparation. Make sure you choose the tag and category before you save the post. Look at the ePortfolio entries of your peers under the tag "values" and leave at least two comments. <p>Tasks for mentors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Read your students' ePortfolio entries in Section "Reflections", Phase Preparation . Apart from that, you are invited to make your own entry on "What you like about teaching" and "Why I decided to become a teacher". Make sure you choose the tag "values". 	Students mainly; Mentors providing feedback	ePortfolio	60 mins
Task 4 Mindmap	Reflecting on key aspects of observation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Think about various aspects of observation in the classroom. Consider WHAT can be observed (team work, assignments, student participation, etc.), HOW it can be observed, think of observation feedback, etc. Create a mindmap on observation and upload it into your ePortfolio. Your mindmap is supposed to illustrate the aspects of observation you regard as the most important ones. You can either use an online tool like https://www.mindmup.com/ or create a pen&paper mindmap. Then take a picture or make a screenshot and copy the picture into the ePortfolio Content Area. Upload your post under the tag "observation". Make sure you choose the tag before you save the post. Look at the mindmaps of your peers to get some additional ideas using the tag "observation". 	Student teachers; mentors providing feedback	Portfolio	60 min.

4. Outline of the EKT SPOC

Task 5 Discussion on Observation	Discussing interesting questions on observation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflect on the topic of observation in the classroom. Answer the questions “What are important aspects and what might be challenges of having an observer in your classroom?” Think about organisational issues like introducing the observer to the students, where the observer will sit, feedback of the observer, peer observation, etc. • Click on the link and answer the two questions in the Communication Tool. • Read the answers of your peers and reply to at least two by using @sign 	ALL	Communication Tool	30 mins
TOTAL WORKLOAD					3 hours

Checklist for Unit 2 Activities:

- I understand the value of Action Research (AR) in the classroom.
- I can give examples and discuss various aspects of observation in the classroom.
- I can make public posts in my ePortfolio and make them private.
- I can comment on the posts of other participants.

4.4. Unit 3 Focus on Professional Dialogue and Reflection

- **Objectives:** to engage the participants in collaborative dialogue around student teachers' inquiry
- **Method:** students start their action-oriented reflection - they turn to academic mentors and school mentors for inquiry support
- **Workload:** for students 3 hours; for academic mentors and school mentors 2 hours

Extra time can be given to work on the final output/entry to the e-potfolio.

Picture 4. Tasks for Unit 3

The screenshot displays the 'EKT Online Course Modules' interface. On the left, a sidebar lists course modules, with 'Unit 3. Focus on Professional Dialogue and reflection' selected. The main content area is titled 'Unit 3 Focus on Professional Dialogue and Reflection' and 'Unit 3. Overview'. It features a 'Tasks' section with two tabs: 'Student Teachers' and 'Academic & School Mentors'. The 'Student Teachers' tab is active, showing the following text:

You will be introduced to a **model for reflection** that deals with the questions: **What? So What? and Now What?**

Apart from that, you will define a research question and engage in a professional dialogue with your mentors and peers to find possible solutions to it. The key value of the exercise is to start looking at the classroom through the **lens of inquiry and reflection** using the expertise of your colleagues and mentors.

Task 1: Text and Video on Reflection (15 min)
 Task 2: Research Question (30 min)
 Task 3: Professional Dialogue (60 min)
 Task 4: Portfolio Entry (45 min)
 Task 5: Sharing your final ePortfolio (30 min)

The 'Academic & School Mentors' tab is also visible, showing the following text:

Student teachers will be introduced to a model for reflection that focuses on the questions **What? So What? and Now What?**

They will define a research question and run through the process of **action-oriented reflection** with your support.

The main objective of this exercise for students is to start looking at the classroom through the **lens of inquiry**, and reflect on their teaching practice, using your experiences and expertise.

4. Outline of the EKT SPOC

nr/name	Aim	Activities	involved	EKT tool	workload
Task 1 Text and Video on Reflection	Getting to know a model for reflection and engaging in reflective writing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Watch the video on reflective practice. • Upload a short text about what you found most important into your ePortfolio under the tag "reflection". 	Student teachers	video	15 min
Task 2 Research Question	Defining your research question determined by your individual teaching context and research interest (= the "what" in the model for reflection)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Think about possible research questions for an Action Research project in the classroom (a question for self-reflection) like "How can I engage students in group work?", "How can I motivate my students to participate more?", etc.) Think of HOW and WHY questions as well. • Define your own research question; determined by your individual teaching context and research interest. • Share it with others and explain your choice using the Communication Tool. • Read the entries of your peers and leave at least 3 comments. 	Student teachers	Communication tool	30 min
Task 3 Professional Dialogue	Finding possible solutions to your research question by discussing it with others (= the "How?" in the model for reflection)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage in a dialogue with your peers (and mentors) and discuss your research question with them. You are encouraged use the Communication Tool to contact peers and your mentors. • Find information and possible solutions (e.g. in literature). 	Student teachers; Mentors supporting student teachers	EKT Communication Tool	60 mins
Task 4 ePortfolio Entry	Reflecting on your research question in your ePortfolio (= the "Now What?" in the model for reflection)	<p>Upload an entry in your ePortfolio in the Section "Reflections", Phase Preparation. Your post should cover the following points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Your research question • Reasons why you chose this question (drawing on your previous training and/or expectations) • What you already knew about the issue • What you learned about the topic from your mentors • What you learned about the topic from your peers • What actions you can take to improve this area of your teaching. <p>Answer the question: What am I going to try out during my in-school placement?</p>	Student teachers	EKT ePortfolio	45 min

<p>Task 5 Sharing and Getting Feedback</p>	<p>Giving and receiving feedback</p>	<p>Task for student teachers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Export the data from your ePortfolio tool as a PDF. Watch a video on how to Export your ePortfolio. • Upload your PDF in the Documents Tool. Watch the video on how to share your document. • Share your PDF with your academic and school mentor(s). <p>Task for mentors:</p> <p>The final output of the course for the student teachers is the story of their development through the process of action-oriented reflection as well as their action plan (action-oriented expectations): how they can try to improve their teaching practice and what they want to try out during the in-school placement.</p> <p>In this task, they are expected to use their reflections on conversations with you and their peers, on their expectations and previous training. Mentors are invited to provide feedback to students and use the rubrics to assess student teachers' inquiries</p>	<p>Student teachers</p> <p>Mentors provide feedback and evaluate following suggested Rubrics</p>	<p>ePortfolio Document Tool</p>	<p>30 min</p>
<p>TOTAL WORKLOAD 3 hours</p>					

Checklist for Unit 3 Activities:

- I can understand and apply the reflective model “What? So What? Now What?”
- I defined a research question I am interested in.
- I talked to my peers and mentors about my area of concern.
- I found possible solutions to the research question.
- I can express my action-oriented interest/expectations for the upcoming in-school placement.
- I shared my ePortfolio texts with my mentors in the Document Tool.

4.5. Unit 4 Creating Educational Materials with Chamilo Studio

Unit 4 is developed for the second pilot of the EKT project and introduces student teachers and mentors to the content creation tool called Chamilo Studio. The tool is designed to create multi-media educational materials like online courses.

- **Objectives:** create multi-media materials using the content creation tool; reflect on expectations for participation in the EKT project; reflect on the importance of digital literacy in the context of teaching and learning;
- **Method:** student teachers are introduced to the Chamilo Studio and create a unit while reflecting on a number of challenge questions.

Workload for student teachers 1 hour.

4. Outline of the EKT SPOC

nr/name	Aim	Activities	involved	EKT tool	workload
Task 1 Chamilo Studio	Getting to know the content creation tool Chamilo Studio	Watch two videos: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • how to access the tool • how to work in Chamilo Studio 	Student teachers	videos	15 min
Task 2 Create eMaterials	Use the tool to create materials; Reflect on expectations for the Project; Reflect on the importance of digital literacy in education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create your own unit with the Chamilo Studio introducing the content that would answer the following questions: • Introduce yourselves as you would do to your pupils. • If you consider your role as a student teacher what are your expectations for the outcomes of the Project? • Where do you see the importance of digital literacy in the context of teaching and learning? • Use various tools to create your content (audio, video, picture, text, mindmap etc.) 	Student teachers	Chamilo Studio	30 min
Task 3 Sharing and Getting Feedback	Sharing the materials and peer learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share the link to your Content in the Group Chat Room • Look at the contents created by other participants in the Chat. 	Student teachers; Feedback from mentors	Chamilo Studio Communication Tool (Chat)	15 min
				TOTAL WORKLOAD	1 HOUR

5. SUPPORTIVE TUTORIAL VIDEOS

5.1. Planning Phase

First, the project partners CESGA, PHWien and Lusoinfo met to discuss the need to create a series of video tutorials that would support the SPOC. Different possibilities were discussed: the number of videos for each platform tool, the approximate length, the use of voiceovers or subtitles, and the default language or languages to be used.

The following decisions were made: the videos should be objective and short enough not to tire the audience. For a better usage, each video should focus on a limited number of functionalities the user could easily understand. The tutorials were planned to be used independently, if needed.

5.2. Production Phases

The first package of 17 videos was produced, according to the developments of the platform. At this stage, the platform already had its entire structure created and the design was the Beta 1 version.

For the second package, after the training tool was developed, the correspondent videos were created. In total 7 tutorial videos.

The third package was produced after three advances had been made in the EKT system: An update on the platform design, the Beta 2 version, the conclusion of the Chamilo Studio tool and the release of the EKT Mobile APP.

5.3. Video production process

5.3.1. Scripts

The scripts were written taking into account the EKT platform structure and the main processes each user should be familiar with. Also relevant were the different types of users, such as Academic mentors, School mentors or Student Teachers, and the fundamental tools and functionalities.

After clarifying the main goals and listing the first package of videos, the next step was to write a script for each of the tutorials. PHWien took the lead on writing the scripts. CESGA and LUSOINFO analyzed and gave feedback.

At this stage LUSOINFO stated the need to create a real world environment in the Platform. The creation of personas that would represent real users and the users structure, chat messages, profile pictures, etc, would allow a more realistic demonstration of the EKT platform dynamics and functionalities.

Lusoinfo then proceeded with the validation of the scripts. It was confirmed whether the technical terms and the explanation of the processes was in accordance with what would be demonstrated on screen. After the necessary adjustments, Lusoinfo advanced to sound recording.

5.4. Sound Recording and editing

As agreed with the partners, it was decided that the videos should be voiced in English. The tutorials would later be published on the EKT Project Youtube Channel. This platform allows the insertion of subtitles in English or in any other language, as long as there is a translation from the original language.

At this stage, sound editing was also carried out to obtain the best quality result. Finally, background music was selected to be used in all the tutorial videos as a way to obtain a sound environment and a sense of unification on all videos.

5.5. Visuals

In this step there was an exploration of the graphic identity of the EKT project, based on the logo and other materials produced by the partner Die Berater. The structural graphic elements and the necessary animations were created:

- Initial screen with the institutional image of the EKT project and dynamic animation;
- Sequence animation with the tutorial identification (Title and subtitle);
- Graphics and other visual elements to complement the information presented in voiceover.

5.6. Video capture

Since the tutorials are based on the EKT platform and on explaining how it works, the video image was essentially made using screen capture software. In this process, the screen capture was carried out taking into account and following the recorded voice for each of the tutorials.

Some visual aspects were also considered, such as the augmented size of the pointer so that the described processes could be more easily followed by the viewer.

5.7. Editing

After creating all the necessary elements, the next step was video editing. This step involved trimming the raw footage, adding transitions, effects, title and subtitles, graphics and the animated sequences. It was also part of this process to add background music and the voiceover.

5.8. Publishing

Once the videos were finished it was time to publish it. The partner Die Berater was responsible to create a youtube account for the EKT project and all the videos were uploaded to this video sharing platform. In this way we were able to embed the videos on the “Help section” of the EKT Platform, and throughout our social media channels.

Below you will find the list of all the tutorial videos used in the SPOC, and being located in the Help Section of the EKT System. The description and link to the videos is provided as well.

Video Title	Description	link
Platform Overview		
1 EKT Platform Overview	In this video you will find a brief description of the main EKT Platform Tools.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HXTzeq2qoa0
2 EKT Platform New Dashboard (Version 2)	In this video, you will learn about new features of the EKT Platform.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UgX7JiwVIJE
Password Recovery		
3 Password Recovery	In this video, you will learn how to change your password for the EKT Platform. (Updated)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ABSaeEz-_TM Updated version: https://youtu.be/ABSaeEz-_T
Management Tool		
4 Management Tool for School Mentors	In this video, you will be introduced to the Management Tool to see the main information about assigned student teachers, school mentors working with them, and you will learn how to edit your profile.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-zV2DI_CZTc
5 Management Tool for Academic Mentors	In this video, you will be introduced to the Management Tool to see the main information about assigned student teachers, academic mentors working with them, and you will learn how to edit your profile.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Fq6ddupfh_E
6 Management Tool for Student Teachers	In this video, you will be introduced to the Management Tool to see the main information about the assigned academic and school mentors, placement school and you will learn how to edit your profile.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Tibt7FLOWgU
Management Tool for University Coordinators		
7 Management	Tool for Coordinators: Overview	In this video, you will learn about the Management Tool and its key elements. The tool is used to create and manage accounts, assign student teachers to mentors, and create courses.
8 Management Tool for Coordinators: Creating Users, Schools, Groups.	In this video you will learn how to create user accounts for different roles, such as academic mentor, school mentor, school coordinator and student teacher.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CJdAAQPzzJw
9 Management Tool: Assigning Student teachers to academic and school mentors, school and group.	In this video, you will learn how to assign student teachers to mentors, groups and schools.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6kChxye2Ugo&t=1s
10 Management Tool: Creating and Assigning a Course.	In this video you will learn how to create an online course, and assign student teachers, academic and school mentors and other roles to it.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Zxs_pw8PIGA

Video Title	Description	link
Documents Tool		
1 Documents Tool Overview	In this video, you will be introduced to the Documents Tool. The tool is used for file management. You will learn about types of folders one can have in the Documents Tool.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WzfbRfhaP0
2 Documents Tool: Shared Group Folders	In this video, you will learn about folders created by default.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fsDvcGwL-2l
3 Documents Tool: Creating and Sharing Private Folders and Files	In this video we will explain how to create private folders and files and share them with a selected group of people.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NrHLuKNh2rg
4 Documents Tool: Collaborative Work in a document	In this video, you will learn what you can do in a document. In the Documents Tool there is a possibility to edit files ((word, excel, etc.) online and collaboratively.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ygmZm6QamIA
Calendar Tool		
1 Calendar Tool: Overview	In this video, we will show you how to use the EKT Calendar and to create a new calendar.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uQwqKmgAlw
2 Calendar Tool: Creating and Sharing an Event	In this video you will learn how to create, and share an event in a calendar, and add a talk room for a meeting or video conference.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-1estbu_FKs
Communication Tool		
1 Communication Tool: Chat Functionality	Communication Tool can be used for a chat and video calls. In this video, you will learn how to have a group chat or send a private message on the EKT Platform.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wvtm_P3FLCc
2 Communication Tool: Video Call	Communication Tool can be used for a chat and video calls. In this video you will learn how to make video calls on the EKT Platform.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=irL6nXUtVFE
3 EKT Communication via mobile app	In this video, you will learn how to download and use the EKT Platform mobile app for easy and quick communication between all involved in the in-school placement.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AsJjODma5j0
Training Tool		
1 Training Tool	In this video, you will learn about the Training Tool of the EKT Platform, and how to access the EKT Online Course	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vd3u3uTPaTO
2 Portfolio Tool: Overview	In this video, you will be introduced to the ePortfolio tool of the EKT Platform; the tool for self-reflection and reflection with peers.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sNONKaoYXKw
3 ePortfolio Tool: Key Actions - 1	In this video, you will learn about the key functionalities of the ePortfolio Tool: how to create a post or entry in your ePortfolio, about the suggested structure of your posts according to the EKT methodology and stages of in-school placement; and how to find posts made by your peers; how to edit or make your posts invisible for others.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=towlDn18TQl
4 ePortfolio Tool: Key Actions - 2	In this video, you will learn how to leave and respond to a comment; and for mentors, how to highlight a comment for student teachers.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QGuTU8mnznQ
5 2 ePortfolio: Commenting a Post	In this video, mentors can learn how to assess student teachers' portfolios: the entire work or specific entries.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vSjoYDtPoSg
6 2 ePortfolio Tool for Mentors: Assessing Student Teacher's Portfolios	In this video, you will learn how to access Chamilo Studio and work in it.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=x6EWfBnbdOE
7 EKT Access to Chamilo Studio	In this video, you will learn how to access Chamilo Studio and work in it.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NRPBI-viifk

6. REFERENCE LISTS

Moore, R. A. 2007. Taking action: Assessing the impact of preservice teaching on learning. *Action in Teacher Education*, 28(3): 53–60.

Kitchen, J., & Stevens, D. (2008). Action research in teacher education: Two teacher-educators practice action research as they introduce action research to preservice teachers. *Action Research* (London, England), 6(1), 7-28. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1476750307083716>

Ross, D. D. (1987). Action research for preservice teachers: A description of why and how. *Peabody Journal of Education*, 64(3), 131-150. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01619568709538562>.

7. ACCESS TO THE SPOC

EKT SPOC visualization links:

English: https://app.ektproject.eu/spoc_en

Spanish: https://app.ektproject.eu/spoc_es

German: https://app.ektproject.eu/spoc_de

Portuguese: https://app.ektproject.eu/spoc_pt

EKT SPOC download links (scorm):

English: <https://cumulo.cesga.es/index.php/s/C4Wctj5o4ZeWQZq>

Spanish: <https://cumulo.cesga.es/index.php/s/sCZcBWkyMg6a4fb>

German: <https://cumulo.cesga.es/index.php/s/pGLmmHs7SnaeXQK>

Portuguese: <https://cumulo.cesga.es/index.php/s/4B6kBzHR6ZDGxis>

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Project Partners

Universidade do Minho

Editor:

Santiago de Compostela: Grupo de investigación de
Tecnología Educativa (USC).
<https://www.tecnoeduc.es/>